

SHORT NOTES

A Note on Alcoholysis Reactions of Alkyl Tellurates

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Following the unsuccessful attempts of Oppenheim¹ and Gutbier² for the synthesis of alkyl tellurates, tellurium hexamethoxide was prepared by Pellini³ in 1916 employing the reaction of diazomethane with telluric acid in methanol :

Patry⁴ reported that, $\text{Te}(\text{OCH}_3)_6$, gradually decomposes to methyl tellurate, $[\text{O}_n\text{Te}(\text{OCH}_3)_n]$ when heated above its melting point. Higher alkyl tellurates, $[\text{O}_n\text{Te}(\text{OR})_n]$ (where R is Et, Prⁿ, Buⁿ and Amⁿ radical) were synthesised by Patry employing the reactions of polymetatelluric acid with alcohols under refluxing conditions :

polymetatelluric acid

These esters were reported to be polymeric in nature.

In view of the interesting results obtained in the synthesis of alkyl selenites⁵ and selenates⁶ as well as tellurium tetraalkoxides⁷ by alcohol interchange technique, it was considered worthwhile to extend similar studies to the synthesis of higher alkyl tellurates also.

On treating ethyl tellurate with a number of alcohols (ROH, where R is Me, Prⁿ, Prⁱ, Buⁿ, Buⁱ, Bu^s, Bu^t, Amⁱ and Am^t radical) in presence of benzene, it was found that contrary to ethyl selenate⁶ which could interchange only one of its ethoxy groups, with normal, secondary and tertiary alcohols, resulting in the formation of mixed alkyl selenates, ethyl tellurate could interchange both its ethoxy groups resulting in the formation of new alkyl tellurates :

By this method it has been possible to synthesise secondary and tertiary alkyl tellurates for the first time.

1. Oppenheim, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1857, 71 II, 275.
2. Gutbier, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1902, 31, 350.
3. Pellini, *Gaz.*, 1916, 46, 247.
4. Patry, *Compt. rend.*, 1936, 202, 2088.
5. Mehrotra and Mathur, *this journal* 1964, 41, 111.
6. Mehrotra and Mathur, *this journal* (Communicated).
7. Mehrotra and Mathur, *this journal*, 1965, 42, 1.

All the alkyl tellurates are either white solids or colourless viscous liquids, soluble in benzene and show polymeric behaviour in this solvent.

EXPERIMENTAL

Throughout the course of the work, all glass apparatus fitted with interchangeable standard ground joints was used. Fractionations were carried out as described earlier³.

All the reagents were dried in the usual manner as described earlier³. Ethyl tellurate was prepared by the method of Patry⁴. Molecular weights were determined in refluxing benzene using a Semimicro Ebulliometer with thermister sensing.

Tellurium was estimated in the elementary form using aqueous solutions of hydrazine hydrochloride and sulphur dioxide as the precipitating agents.

The alkoxy content in the ethoxy and isopropoxy derivatives, and ethanol in the azeotrope was estimated by an oxidimetric method⁵.

1. *Reaction between ethyl tellurate and n-propanol.*—To ethyl tellurate (0.95 g.) was added n-propanol (20 g.) followed by the addition of benzene, thereby causing an endothermic reaction. The reaction mixture was refluxed under a column for about four hours and the liberated ethanol was fractionated azeotropically with benzene at 68°. Excess of the solvents were distilled out at the column at a high reflux ratio and on finally drying the contents at 80°/0.5 mm a colourless viscous liquid (1.06g., 100%), soluble in benzene was obtained. Found: Te, 45.96%. Mol. Wt., 2286. Calc. for $O_2Te(OPr^i)_2$: Te, 45.92%; Mol. Wt., 277.8

2. *Preparation of methyl tellurate.*—Excess of methanol followed by benzene was added to ethyl tellurate (1.42g.). The reaction was found to be weakly endothermic. The contents were subjected to distillation and the process was repeated until the temperature of the distilling liquid did not show any tendency of rising above 57°. Excess of the solvents were distilled out and finally the contents were dried at 60°/10.5 mm. to a white solid (1.20g., 100%) soluble in benzene. Found: Te, 57.25%. Calc. for $O_2Te(OMe)_2$: Te, 57.54%.

For brevity the results of these two and other similar reactions are recorded in the Table I.

TABLE I

S. No.	Reagents (g.)	Product and state of yield	Yield	Analysis							
				%Te		%OR		Alcohol in azeotrope(g.)		Mol. Wt.	
				Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
1.	Ethyl tellurate (1.42) + Methanol (excess)	$O_2Te(OMe)_2$ A white solid	1.20g., 100%	57.25	57.54	—	—	—	—	—	—
2.	Ethyl tellurate (0.95) + n-Propanol (20)	$O_2Te(OPr^i)_2$ A colourless viscous liquid	1.06g., 100%	45.96	45.92	—	—	—	—	228.6	277.8

TABLE I (contd.)

S. No.	Reagents (g.)	Product and state of yield	Yield	Analysis						Mol. Wt.	
				%Te		%OR		Alcohol in azeotrope(g.)		Found	Calc.
				Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.		
3.	Ethyl tellurate (1.72) + Isopropanol (19)	$O_2Te(OPr)_2$ A colourless viscous liquid, solidifying on keeping.	1.91g., 100%	45.53	45.92	40.15	42.58	—	—	232	277.8
4.	Ethyl tellurate (0.90) + n-Butanol (15)	$O_2Te(OBu^n)_2$ A colourless viscous liquid	1.10g., 100%	41.35	41.74	—	—	—	—	157	305.7
5.	Ethyl tellurate (1.90) + Isobutanol (24)	$O_2Te(OBu^i)_2$ A colourless viscous liquid	2.43g., 100%	41.55	41.74	—	—	—	—	154	305.7
6.	Ethyl tellurate (1.38) + Sec. butanol (19)	$O_2Te(OBu^s)_2$ A colourless viscous liquid	1.60g., 94%	41.79	41.74	—	—	—	—	170	305.7
7.	Ethyl tellurate (1.30) + Tert. butanol (28)	$O_2Te(OBu^t)_2$ A white solid	1.50g., 94%	41.43	41.74	—	—	0.46	0.48	—	—
8.	Ethyl tellurate (1.37) + Isopentanol (12)	$O_2Te(OAm^i)_2$ A colourless viscous liquid	1.82g., 99%	37.93	38.30	—	—	—	—	104	333.9
9.	Ethyl tellurate (1.35) + Tert. pentanol (12)	$O_2Te(OAm^t)_2$ A white solid	1.80g., 100%	37.84	38.30	—	—	0.48	0.50	—	—

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